

#1

Evaluation & Impact Assessment

PARTICIPATORY SOCIAL NETWORK MAPPING & APPRAISAL

<p>MAA Scenario</p> <p>ENGAGING & INCENTIVISING</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>Crucial at team-building stage and used iteratively throughout project/initiative to assess and improve network membership and collaborative relationships.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>Small to large multi actor group.</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>No technical skills required.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>20mins-1.5 hrs mins (depending on group size & extent of discussion).</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>Very low, requires basic materials. Can be conducted physically with participants in a room or on an online platform such as Klaxoon, Pinup, or Mural. At least one facilitator is required.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tools # 2, 9, 11, 13, 26, 27, 28.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

Purpose

This tool is used to:

- Assess the types of actors involved in multi-actor teams, and the actors who may not but who ought to be involved.
- Sensitise and attune participants to the actor categories they are representing in multi-actor teams.
- Assess strengths and weaknesses of cooperative relationships within multi-actor teams.
- Identify and plan actions to exploit strengths and address weaknesses.
- Periodically assess changes in strengths and weaknesses of the network, also considering stakeholders (representativeness of and relationships within the network)

Image source: Photo by Paul Hanaoka on Unsplash

Background and Logic

Consensus is not always the main objective of multi-actor work, the aim is to draw out the different knowledges, perspectives and ideas that different actors have. It is important, thus, especially in the earliest stages of group formation, to appraise who is in the group and to allow each actor to make explicit their sectoral background and identity, and the associated knowledges, perspectives etc. that they bring. Because the objective and purpose of multi-actor approaches is to bring diverse actors together, it is very important for the actors involved to be aware of differences between actors in the group; and to periodically revisit how their different orientation is influencing the multi-actor process. Furthermore, it is necessary to appraise and evaluate group membership to establish whether the group is sufficiently diverse, balanced, and representative of all the actor cohorts who should be involved. This tool can also be used as an ice-breaker, when bringing a group of actors together for the first time, supporting group members to claim particular actor identities from the earliest stages of a project and to attune members of the group to differences in the group, preparing for future potential to exploit those differences

Materials

- Flip chart paper
- Sticky notes
- Thick dark markers

METHOD/HOW TO GUIDE

Step1

- Explain the purpose, logic and background of the exercise.
- Ask participants to write their name and an 'actor identifier' on a sticky note (either physically in an in-person meeting or virtually, using an appropriate platform such as Klaxoon, Mural, Pinup etc.)
- Actor identifiers depend on the orientation of the multi-actor project. For example, in a Horizon 2020 Thematic Network, the actor identifiers may include research, education, SME and extension. The diversity of actors (and their actor identifiers) are typically cited in funding applications, as a credential of the project's multi-actor approach. The group can be reminded of the importance of including different actor categories, and asked to reflect on the actor category they are representing in the group/network/project
- It is important to explain to the group that some actors may have other/several actor identifiers. Ask them to reflect on the particular role/s they will/ have in the project in choosing their actor identifiers. They may choose more than one identifier, but it is important for actors to represent the actor category/ies they are representing in the project/ assigned in a grant agreement, where relevant.
- It is possible, such as in the example pictured on the right, to use icons to structure how actors identify the category to which they belong. This may be pertinent in projects such as Horizon 2020 projects, that

Step 2

- In a small group (up to 12) ask participants to cluster the sticky notes according to group identifiers. In a larger group, identify a representative from each actor category and invite them to approach the board and cluster the sticky notes according to actor categories. In the example to the right, participants have grouped the sticky notes into two categories: farmers and extension.
- Ask participants to draw a circle around the clustered post-its and to assign them an actor category label. In the example to the right, two labels are created: farmers and extension.
- Now we can see a graphical representation of the actor categories represented in the group, who is in the categories, and the numbers of actors in each of the categories.
- Facilitate a discussion around the following types of questions:
 - » Is the group/network balanced in terms of who is represented and the number of actors representing various categories?
 - » Is there any type of actor missing, who should be invited to become involved?

Step 3

- In a small group (up to 12) ask participants to draw lines between their actor category and any actor category/ies they are collaborating with. Thick lines can be drawn to indicate strong cooperation/sharing of resources. Thin or broken lines can be drawn to indicate undeveloped or cooperative relationships.
- We should see from this graphical representation of cooperative relationships, the relationships that are strong, relationships that need development, and relationships that are absent and need to be built.

Step 4

On the basis of how the group has sketched details of who is represented in the group/network, facilitate a discussion of topics such as:

- How were strong cooperative relationships built and what can we learn from this to make other relationships stronger?
- What actions can we take to develop relatively weak relationships and collaborations?
- What actions can we take to build new relationships with actors who should be represented in the group/network but are currently absent?
- Optionally, the actions can be recorded on sticky notes and planned using the figure (as shown on the right).

Step 5

- Use the social network map generated in Step 3 periodically in team meetings to:
- Remind/attune members to the sector they are representing in the multi-actor process, and ask their perspectives about what actors within their sector might think or want at various stages of the project's evolution.
- Revisit the discussions and actions identified in Step 4 to regularly assess the network and how it may be improved (in terms of the representativeness of the network and collaborative relationships within it).
- Update the map periodically to reflect changes/forms of progress made in the network.
- It is important to note that this exercise may also be extended to assessing interactions and relationships with stakeholders as the project progresses and impacting *stakeholders* becomes more important.

